

Factors Influencing Compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety: A Case Study of Amazon

BY

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management systems utilizing Amazon as a case study. The study also established Challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States; Identified factors promoting compliance of ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company. A descriptive research design will be used in this study. Positivism is employed to pursue this study. The researcher adopts an inductive approach in an attempt to develop ideal questions in order to collate valid data from workers of Amazon Company in the United State of America; this is necessary as the philosophy associated type is quantitative. The data were collected from 108 staff of Amazon's company in the United State of America. A descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, sample frequency, and percentage was used to described the demographic data of the respondents and to answer research questions respectively.

The result showed that: i. establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces; ii. Providing education and capacity-building opportunities for the employee and often providing advisory service; iii. Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization; iv. creation of an enabling environment that allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization; v. optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to the safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment; and vi. The availability of provision for safety equipment or workable systems culture, in order to promote a healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization, is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented were identified as the factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

The challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety standard in Amazon Company are; i. the cost attached to health and safety management system under the motivational variables, ii. ISO 45001 itself, expensive cost of 45001 Health and Safety implementation as well as certification, iii. risk assessment from the external support of consulting firms. This implies that the problems confronting the compliance of employees to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in United States was as a result of the cost required from staff to pay out of their salaries for the return of the services rendered to them by the Health and Safety management. The expensive nature of the cost attached to adoption of ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in United States would either way cause disloyalty from the path of the workers and denial to accept the policy stipulated under ISO 45001 itself.

The research objective two (2) was to identify the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America. The study conclusions on objective two (2) suggested that; i. the establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces; ii. Educational provision and capacity building opportunity for the employee and often provide advisory service; iii. Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization; iv. creation of enabling environment which allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization; optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment; and v. the availability of provision for safe equipments or workable systems culture for the promotion of healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization as the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

The study therefore recommended that the company head should be ready for sensitizing their employees on the importance of their adherence to principles and policies if ISO45001 for Occupational Health and Safety system, thereby stating all requirements and likely implications attracted by their failure to comply accordingly. Also, the company should take appropriate steps to fine tune the challenges encountered for the achievement of employees adherence to the policy of ISO45001. The employer should ensure adequate establishment of advisory service on a regular basis, the will be of great assistance, as the process will be use to persuade and encourage the employees to show positive attitude to the company's stated policies as regards to their compliance rules and regulations of ISO45001 for Occupational Health and safety system to take its full implementation in the company.

The research objective two (2) was to identify the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America. The study recommended that Amazon's company should be ready to adopt an ideal control measure in their company, most especially in the production department. Implementation of such baseline will go a long way to forestall appropriate direction and will make it easy to coordinate the overall affairs of the workers in term of cooperativeness to authority and command.

The company department leaders should also ensure to build cordial relationship with the inferior employee, this will enable free flow of information and interactions about all that is beneficial can be easily included among the matter arising or discussion point such like having a sensitization talk for few minutes to buy their interest to render appropriate support for the adherence to ISO45001 for Occupational Health and Safety.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

A. Research Background

The policy named ISO 45001 is a new development system tagged as the implementation of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) which initiation aims was targeted at maintenance and assurance of hazardous activities related to Occupational Health and safety management in an organization, especially meant for the labor workforce to enhance productiveness, efficaciousness turn-over, and all-round development. The implementation of ISO 45001 also known as Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) is used interchangeably to help an organization convert threats emanating from dangerous occurrences to opportunities also to take charge to have the capacity to forestall desirable growth and development. However, every employee deserves safety and a secured work-life which requires assurance from the employers; this is considered necessary to be put in place for the workers for it will assist to boost the morale to work willingly in an efficient manner towards the progress of their host establishment.

The obligation of the employer is to ensure that workers are healthy and always feel secure in every aspect related to work and to also assure the employees of the availability of preventive measures as related to dealing with hazardous situations and associated risk in the working environment gave birth to new Occupational Health and safety management in an organization which is tagged as the implementation of Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) to ISO45001 was developed on OHSAS ISO 18001 which was recognized as a standard (ISO 2018). Moreover, the integration of this design into an organization could only be valid if its adoption and implementation are done in an existing management process which must be in line with the same high-level structure as other ISO management system standards, such as ISO 9001 (quality management) and ISO 14001 (environmental management). However, this ISO 45001 management System in an organization is responsible for the care of potential hazards associated with occupational health and safety (OH&S) risks and with the aim of ensuring performance improvement by developing and implementing effective policies and objectives.

The health and safety of the employees should be considered utmost among the factors responsible to enhance rapid improvement in the productivity and workforce in an ideal organization. For instance, according to a more recent calculation by the International Labor Organization (ILO), 2.78 million deaths take place every year as a result of work. That is to say, nearly 7700 persons die daily resulting from diseases and injuries that are work-related (ILO, 2018). In such case, enhancement of Return of Investment is most desirable for effective implementation of ISO 45001 as well as aligning productivity with identifying and adopting a qualitative approach to deal with hazards and associated risks and also develop preventive measures to reduce incidents as low as reasonably practicable. ISO 45001 is the implementation through which low insurance premium is equally achieved, applications of ISO 45001 shall place operations in Amazon Inc on the pinnacle of business as an organization which will bring about gaining employees honesty and trust leading to totally embracing of ISO 45001, boosting morale to work willingly which in-turn serves as a promotion of efficiency and productiveness. Both the risk and opportunities leveraged by ISO 45001 Outweighs ISO (ISO 2018). In the light of the above backdrop information, this study seeks to investigate the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety utilizing Amazon as a case study.

B. Background of Amazon

Amazon is an online retailing website founded by Jeff Bezos, a computer science and electrical engineering graduate from Princeton University around the year 1995 and 1997. It was designed for the aim of providing a large coverage of customers both locally and internationally with low prices, a wide selection, ease of website use, and the convenience to meet all of its consumers' needs in one virtual store which makes it an urban legend of its time. The Amazon website also hosts products from a variety of sellers, who

enjoy the benefits of the Amazon brand. This allows them to reach a much larger customer base than they could reach on their own.

The emergence of the company was born out of the growth brought by the advent of modern technology upon instance experience to the extent to which the Internet was growing at 2300% in 1994; this period set a pace for the creation of Amazon to cling to a large growth opportunity (Bezo 1998). The company running relies upon E-Commerce retailing with the formation to start its business as a bookseller at the beginning, which was afterward diversified to varieties retail types that today morphed into the world's largest online retailer by offering DVDs, apparel, electronics, computers, toys, jewelry, furniture, shoes, movies, games, music, sports including outdoor gear, auto parts, home and garden, grocery, health and beauty, and digital downloads which finally was introduced to the online buyers and the general public within the year range of July 1995 and May 1997 (Amazon.com 1999; McGraw-Hill Companies 2012).

Notably, today Amazon company serves in four different customer types, including enterprises, final consumers, sellers, and content creators, and ensured that the middlemen retailers are logically eliminated in the supply chain; this enables the direct flow of negotiation on contracts from their worldwide customers and publishers, building large warehouses, and leveraging expertise from various hired executives like Wal-Mart and others (Hof 2008). The company Web Services also offers technology infrastructure that can be utilized by enterprises ranging in size and business focus in accordance to associated independent publishers and authors that are usually given a 70% royalty option when they choose to sell their books in the Kindle store through Kindle Direct Publishing. Finally, the company has achieved its objective by currently being among the first five (5) online retailing websites to build the world's most customer-centric company and has also established a recognized platform place where customers could buy anything (Piacentini 2000; Streitfeld 2012).

C. Statement of the Problem

The compliance to implementation of the new ISO 45001 for the management of associated occupational health and safety by Amazons' company is at a low extent despite the fact that have been among the global largest business organization (Amazon Injury Data, 2021). The need for compliance to this new system is necessary to remediate the damages caused by an occupational hazard (facility induced damages, environmental and ash policies) considerably when taking into account the evolution of other past management systems approaches that failed due to lack of appropriate implementation, such as low quality, un-standardized policy, and unhealthy environment. However, it was observed that in Amazon company within a year or lesser that in every 15 seconds, a worker dies from a work-related illness or disease while others sometimes suffer several work-related accidents. For instance, the SOC Survey of Amazon Workers (2021) reported that a total of 996 Amazon workers responded to the survey conducted on the analysis of Amazon's injury data related to health and safety issues at their Amazon workspaces between February 12 and February 18, 2021. The results show that virtually all reported victims are working in one of four segments of Amazon's operations: making a total of (52%) from fulfillment centers, 24% of last-mile delivery, 9% of delivery stations, and 8% sortation centers. More so, in another similar case of 4 in 10 (42%) and 8 in 10 Amazon workers working at facilities in forty-two different states, with the largest concentrations in Florida, California, Texas, Ohio, and New Jersey reported experiencing pain or injury incurred from the execution of their assigned duties that caused them to miss work, and other production-related pressure or speed. It is so disheartening that the management of Amazon companies has little or no knowledge about the negative effect occupational risk has on employee health and safety. If ISO 45001 is not duly complied to, automatically the health and safety of the employees is deemed to be at nothing but awkward condition, and this would in turn mar overall progress in the production turn-over of the organization.

Based on the ongoing backdrop information this study is set out to examine the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety utilizing Amazon as a case study.

D. Aims and Objective of the Study

The general aim of the study is to investigate the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management systems utilizing Amazon as a case study.

E. The specific objectives are to:

- To establish Challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States.
- To Identify factors promoting compliance of ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon company.

F. Research Questions

- What are the Challenges facing compliance to ISO 450001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States?
- What are the associated factors that promote compliance to ISO 450001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States?

G. Justification and Significance of the Study

It is generally known that one of the major reasons Occupational Health and safety management system is put in place is to cater for the would-be potential hazards that could be incurred as a result of the occupation, thereby make appropriate provisions that will be responsible for aversion orsway potential hazards that could be perceived to mar the productiveness and efficaciousness of the workforce as a result of individual exposure to occupational risks. To this end, any study that is being carried out with the intention of finding ways in which the staff in an organization will be saved from hazardous occupational risk which would in-turn be responsible for the reformation of threats emanating from harmful circumstances into the befitting moment with the capability to stimulate positive turn-over, productiveness, and all-round development to make occupational activities easier is definitely worth carrying out.

The study will be of immense importance to Amazon management in that it would give broader information on the internal and external factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 standards by employees. The implication of this study would be an immense benefit to the committee in charge of occupational risk, for it would tender strategies for successful implementation of ISO 45001 in an organization. It would also assist the producing companies like Amazon, SWOT, Target, Netflix, Apple, Google, etc. in the adoption of task-specific standard operating procedures as a guideline for compliance to standards by employees and management. Furthermore, it will also be of benefit to the risk management trainer in that it would provide introductory information for standardized training of ISO 45001 in accordance to utilizing SWOT Analysis to determine the effect of internal and external factors on ISO 45001 effective implementation and would give details related to the exploration of the benefit of standard improvement in an organization.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Literature Review

Adherence to the implementation of ISO 45001 policies is highly germane for overall organizational growth and development. This is necessary for ensuring employee safety and health is under good control; as every successful organization's credibility can never be adequate without giving due credence to the efforts of its employees. These employees deserve a healthy life and an enabling working environment absolutely free from danger. Good health and a secure work-life is the main ingredient for an effective workforce. However, if consideration of ISO 45001 for occupational health and safety implementation is put in place by employers to ensure the all-round progress of their host workers in the organization. In order to determine the success of ISO 45001 implementation done by the management system in an organization, employees' compliance to every fundamental policy initiated for the improvement of quality organization's workforce efficiency of input towards the achievement of tangible turn-over in the overall productivity is most desirable. Thus, consideration has to be given to various challenges facing compliance to Occupational Health and Safety standards in organizational settings.

The employee's compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system can be affected by certain factors like the introduction of new production equipment or machines, market competition or demand pressure, swift change to new products, political instability caused by unexpected global disease out-break and contextual restructure of the organization. Ultimately, employee's non-compliance to ISO 45001 could automatically expose them to high-risk operations and be liable for the continual occurrence of dangers that would emerge from a working environment, which gap should have been covered by due compliance to the management system policy.

However, a poor Occupational Health and Safety culture discourages an emollient atmosphere where there is conformity to safe working practices, and so causes hindrance to the exploration of productiveness and efficient action taken by the organization to solve health and safety problems (Turner, Pidgeon, Blockley & Toft 1989). Also, similar studies on factors affecting the implementation of OHS management systems showed management commitment, staff participation, OHS training plus standard objectives were identified as instrumental to the implementation of OHS management systems (Poon, et al. 2000).

In another related study on the impact of OHS factors affecting construction workers' behavior in different construction projects, the result showed that management commitment linked with OHS policies, health care, communication, education, and training plays a vital part in sustaining a hazard-free workplace in building construction projects (Silaparasetti, Rao & Khan 2017). Thus, industries faced challenges in implementing OSH programs like; lack of cooperation from employees, difficulties in interpreting OSH statutory requirements, lack of management commitment, and so on as a result of the absence of capacity-building opportunities made available for the employees (Ndegwa, 2015).

Studies on leadership effect on OHS were done by Lievens and Vlerick (2014); Clarke and Ward (2006); Clarke (2013) and Grill, Pousette, Nielsen, Grytnes, and Törner (2017). Gill et al., examined safety leadership to assess the influence of different leadership styles on safety climate, safety behavior, and accidents in the Swedish and Danish construction industry. The random sample of 811 construction workers from 85 sites answered the given questionnaire. It was concluded that leadership behaviors influence safety outcomes in Sweden and Denmark; thus, applying less laissez-faire leadership and more transformational, active transactional, participative and rule-oriented leadership appears to be an efficient way for construction site managers to improve OHS in the industry. Both Clarke (2013) and Clarke and Ward (2006) investigate the effect of leader influence tactics on employee safety participation. Studies show that leadership styles have varied influences on safety observance and participation – so, training and development plans should

make explicit ties between leader behavior and their positive influence on employee behavior. Thus, leaders may well promote safety participation using a combination of influence tactics, based on logical arguments, involvement in decision making, and creating enthusiasm for safety.

Channeling of workforce towards working proficiently to attain worldwide recognition of the organization, consistently work diligently towards the progress of the organization, focus on organizational work success, high increment in the return on organization investment, clear identification of work likes associated risk and hazard linked with appropriate remediation strategies are majorly implication of the employee's compliance to ISO 45001 management system and there would be a reduction in incident rate if Amazon effectively implements ISO 45001 for health and safety management. This would be an added value by employees to Amazon's business profile due to their vicious compliance to ISO 45001. Although the above-stated point is already assured under the general benefit that would be accrued as a result of adherence to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system to promote employees efficiency in striving for organizational success, it is not clear if the intended outcome is always achieved. However, the ongoing study would give further insight with detailed information as drawn from the findings.

Kotongiannis et al. (2016) further added that ISO 45001 for health and safety management is imperative for the achievement of total high satisfaction for organizations to be constantly focused on knowing, eliminating, decreasing, and controlling reasons that interrupt and compromise the anticipated overall performance and procedures which can be concentrated on Occupational Health and safety risk management system. This would be extra benefits over others that don't view occupational health and safety risk management systems as an added-value; being negligent to safety will negatively affect the business enterprise sustainability (Campailaet *al.* 2019).

The factors promoting compliance of ISO 45001- health and safety standards are related to serving several purposes, acting as procedures and motivational tools used among the employer and the employee. To support this statement, Geller (2005) reported that setting a fundamental principles is among the factors to guide policies to encourage compliance of Occupational Health and Safety management system to be effectively implemented: action and management; general protection measures, for example, guarding of machinery, medical examination of young workers or limiting the weight of loads to be transported by a single worker; protection in specific branches of economic activity, such as mining, the building industry, commerce and dock work; protection of specific professions (for example, factory workers and seafarers) and categories of workers having particular occupational health needs (such as women or young workers); protection against specific risks (ionizing radiation, benzene, asbestos); prevention of occupational cancer; control of air pollution, noise and vibration in the working environment; measures to ensure safety in the use of chemicals, including the prevention of major industrial accidents; organizational measures and procedures relating to labor inspection or compensation for occupational injuries and diseases.

Hughes and Ferrett (2011) submitted that safety management is necessary at times to hold people accountable for doing the right things for injury prevention. However, management alone is not enough to achieve and sustain an injury-free workplace. Ontario Ministry of Labor (2013) submitted that ISO 45001 enables an organization to identify OH&S hazards, risks, and opportunities to proactively manage to support worker wellness/well-being. The ISO 45001 standard calls for the organization's management and leadership to integrate responsibility for health and safety issues as part of the organization's overall plan, demonstrate engagement with employees (and where they exist employees' representatives) to create an organizational culture that encourages the active participation of workers in the OH&S management system, as well as ensure the integration of OH&SMS into an organization's business process. Others are to: Understand and determine the scope and issues (positive and negative) that can affect how an organization manages the OH&S management system, determine risk and opportunities, develop or enhance OH&S policy and set objectives, and as well as to gain a high-level understanding of needs and expectations of workers and other interested parties (and differences for managerial and non-managerial workers)

Employees are the main target of ISO 45001 management system initiation and implementation which value should be considered to bring additional promotion of business profile. These employees' values could be determined from the extent to which they perform efficiently towards the growth of the organization (NOSA 2011). This means the willingness of the employee to productively strive with a purposeful determination at discharging assigned duties, would immensely add value to the productivity of the company. NOSA (2011) further explores the general duties of employees at work stated under OHS ACT section 14. The research showed every employee is responsible to take adequate care of themselves, ensure proper safety of other persons who may be affected by his act or omissions, see to the accomplishment of Organizational Health and Safety management system goals in collaboration with their employer, explore and enforce lawful order assigned to them by the organizational management and oblige to the rules and procedures laid down by the regulatory body within the health and safety management system, make prompt report of any unsafe situation or unhealthy instances observe to the safety representative and employer as practically possible before it transcends to cause injury or accident (NOSA, 2011).

Similarly, some procedures and strategies for promoting OHS in Organizations include; establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces, providing education and capacity building opportunities for the employee and often provide advisory services, introducing motivational programs, and heightening sensitization. Equip and expose workers with the knowledge of their OHS rights and responsibilities, noting its essentiality to prepare them for ideal compliance to OHS practices and to respond promptly to OHS issues and hazards (Ontario Ministry of Labor, 2013). Furthermore, Hughes & Ferrett, (2011) submitted that the status given to health and safety and the number of resources (money, time, and people) serves as the best indicator of the employer's concern for health and safety as shown by such allocation made available to health and safety needs of the organization.

Additionally, the factors responsible for promoting compliance of ISO 45001- health and safety standards in an organization should absolutely comprise the combinations of enabling interactions between the working environment, equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization. These organizations should place optimal consideration to the attitudes and values attached to safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment. Also, adequate provision should be made for safe equipment or workable systems culture, in order to promote a healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization (IOSH–Institution of Occupational Safety and Health–UK 2015).

Chen et al., (2009) also confirmed that top management's commitment and support were instrumental to the enforcement of OHS management systems. However, motivational factors prior to making decisions to introduce OHS management systems in an organization are highly germane to promote employee compliance to Occupational Health and safety policies (Podgórski 2006). More so, Clarke (2013) reported that economic incentives, promoted training packages on OSH management, and improved involvement in OSH activities were instrumental factors to implementation of OSH management systems in enterprises in Poland.

According Walters and Nichols' (2006) joint arrangements in which workers are represented and consulted on their HS gives room for better safety outcomes that in-turn promotes relationship between management consultation on general issues and those of health and safety. Also, employee capacity building opportunity sought to establish the relative efficacy of various means of worker safety and health training, so as to ensure safety knowledge is given to improve performance and reducing negative outcomes like accidents, illnesses, and injuries (Serafin, Salvador, and Islam 2006).

Another quasi-experimental study showed that active participation of workers proved greater knowledge acquisition, and reductions were seen in accidents, illnesses, and injuries (Sar 2009). Also, Vinodkumar and Bhasi (2010) identified safety training opportunities made available by the employer, as being the most crucial safety management practice that made it easy to forecast safety knowledge, safety

motivation, need in safety compliance, and safety participation. While, Sar, (2009) found that employee training has a very positive effect on the OHS.

An adequate compliance to ISO 45001- occupational health and safety policies is imperative for the achievement of improved management support, ideal employee training, legal framework, and employee participation resulting in the enhanced implementation of the OSH program (Thuo & Wanyonyi 2012). On the contrary, low literacy levels of workers, managers' ignorance of OHS responsibilities, and ineffective OHS administration are basic factors hindering the capacity of construction SMEs to manage OHS effectively (Kheni, Gibb, and Dainty 2010). Gaceri (2015) also examined the factors determining the implementation of HS in Supermarkets. According to the research study, it was established that quality leadership style, employee training, and employee participation influenced the implementation of HS measures in supermarkets in Kenya. The participative approach on its own can bring in improvements on OHS as such managers are advised to share OHS information with employees in order to consolidate individualized relationships with them.

The level at which safety management practices affect safety behaviors has been explored noting some severe risk factors and emerging issues in the OSH realm, thereby indicate procedures on how to improve counteractive measures, nurture safety-related behaviors, how OHS management impacts organizations, and their staff (Vinodkumar & Bhasi 2010). Also, in the attempt to determine the relationship between OHS practices and organizational performance or how a single variable such as training, employees' participation, and how other variables affect OHS (Kalmi & Kauhanen 2010).

The ISO 45001 improvement could only be in its full practices when there are effective policies guiding the management of the incident, nonconformity, and corrective action to promote continual improvement. Since the primary purpose of implementing an OHS management system is to prevent fatalities, injuries, and ill health, the potential importance should be placed on the extent at which it policies device better tools for the management of OH&S risks, improvement in organizational OHS performance, protection of the total workforce from such activities that could be harmful to both employer and employees, better identification of opportunities to improve OHS management, allows fora better approach to incident investigation, adoption of a more cooperative culture for greater worker engagement and empowerment, encourage pursuance of positive OHS initiatives that are compatible with your business priorities and improvements in the production process and service quality. However, if employees are exposed to better workplace morale, improved style of employee recruitment and retention in line with a more favorable image and reputational response from customers, suppliers, and the community, then the new ISO 45001 associated with occupational health and safety would be considered to have taken its full position as being the best policies to implement for appropriate organizational management of risk (Gaceri 2015). Thus, new technologies, good practices of both internal and external to the organization, suggestions, and recommendations from interested parties, new knowledge and understanding of OHS issues which is relevant for the achievement of organizational goal and new or improved modern materials for swift changes in worker capabilities or competence are considerable instruments require for use in this context to focus on the identification of ISO 45001 opportunities with fewer resources. In each case, attention should be paid to a proper risk assessment prior to implementing the improvement resulting from the above-mentioned opportunities (Rotich &Kwasira 2015).

The studies mentioned provide some information on the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety utilizing Amazon as a case study. This research study will provide further information about the value employees would add to Amazon's business profile with the compliance to ISO 45001, give more detail on the implication of organization compliance to implementation of ISO 45001 for health and safety management on reduction of incident rate in Amazon. Also, the study will focus on identifying the factors influencing Amazon compliance to ISO 45001 policies as there is currently a few research studies about this. It is important to know as the implications may be different. Occupational Health and safety are essential for the achievement of organizational success. Similarly, this study will give further information on

identifying the factors promoting compliance of ISO 45001- health and safety standards in the Amazon company. The failure to comply with policies of ISO 45001- health and safety standards by the organization are often the reason why employees are exposed to awkward working conditions and other work-related pressure, accidents and automatically causes regression in the production turn-over of the organization. When employers fulfill the obligation by making appropriate provisions for enabling an environment free from danger and related occupational accidents, employees become masters at giving their best to work efficiently and productively towards the success and progress of the organization. High Productivity may become continuous, as it yields a positive reputation from customers in the delivery of quality products and services. Thus, this is a tangible necessity for the formulation of this research, as it was worthy of investigation.

B. Research Process

A Positivism research philosophy is employed to pursue this study. This means obtaining valid data and understanding of its translations will be sequentially arranged in a purposeful manner. This research philosophy is chosen, for it empirically gives a direct indication of aspect representing truth in an investigated phenomenon (Guba & Lincoln 1994: 110). Also, Positivism research philosophy has the capability to study a phenomenon without influencing it or being influenced by it, thereby making its inquiry processes through a one-way mirror. The research methodology associated with this type of philosophy is quantitative. This study will use the mono quantitative methodology to collect data. A survey with a series of well-structured questionnaires will be sent across respondents for appropriate administration of the instrument. This survey method is chosen, as it is considered to be the most suitable procedure to utilize for this nature of research and to gather primary data. The survey will be sent to a specific section in Amazon Company. In order to provide reasonable answers to the purpose of this study and to collect accurate primary data, a quantitative methodology in terms of survey design will be employed, as it comprises predefined variables and data related to close-ended information. Questions in the survey are designed to answer the research questions and understand the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon Company.

A non-probability convenience sampling technique will be utilized in this study. This procedure implies not giving the overall members of the population the opportunity to participate equally as being represented through selection in this research. Chosen respondents will rely upon the availability and willingness of the targeted sample to partake in this study. This is also a peculiar procedure to employ, as the respondents will come from different departments and the survey cannot include the entire population of every department in Amazon Company due to limited time. Respondents will be employees from different departments included under the compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon Company.

A cross-sectional type of survey design will be employed, as it will be distributed at one specific point in time. The questionnaires will also be distributed to the selected respondents in the Company. The researcher would ensure prompt completion and returns of all copies of the questionnaire. The completed copies of the questionnaires would be retrieved immediately from the respondents for a faster and automated collection of data. Once the data is received from all the respondents, the data will be managed and analyzed. When the analysis is done, the findings will be described. A meaningful and logical conclusion will be drawn from the findings.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction

This chapter presents the modalities and strategies that would be adopted in the conduct of this study. It would consist of: Research Onion, Research Philosophy, Research Approach, Research Design, Data Source, Data Collection Method, Population and Sampling, Ethics, Reliability and Validity, and Rationale for the study. Thus, the research methodologies will be discussed under the following sections:

B. Research Onion

The researcher employs the Onion model proposed by Saunders (2007) to explain the research process, for an appropriate understanding of how the research methodology was formulated in line with the connections between research philosophies, research approaches, research strategies, time horizons, research techniques, and research procedures. However, this present study onion model stage consists of five different sections. In the first section, positivism research philosophy; In the second section, the researcher adopts an inductive approach in an attempt to develop an ideal question to collate valid data from workers of Amazon Company in the United State of America; In the third section, a survey research strategies will be utilized; meanwhile, in the fourth section, the time horizon to collect data for this study will be a cross-sectional type; while, in the fifth section, questionnaire and secondary data will be used in the process.

C. Research Philosophy

Positivism is employed to pursue this study. This means obtaining valid data and understanding of its translations will be sequentially arranged in a purposeful manner. This research philosophy is chosen, for it empirically gives a direct indication of the aspect representing truth in an investigated phenomenon (Sam, 2012).

D. Research Approach

The researcher adopts an inductive approach in an attempt to develop ideal questions in order to collate valid data from workers of Amazon Company in the United State of America; this is necessary as the philosophy associated type is quantitative.

E. Research Design

A descriptive research design will be used in this study. This is chosen because it will accurately provide information on the study by making necessary explanations in systemic ways of valid precisions about a certain phenomenon. According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2009), descriptive research is the quest to provide an accurate description of observations of a phenomenon. Thereby added that the main reason for the collection of census data is to accurately describe basic information about a national population at a particular point in time.

F. Data Source

➤ *Primary Source*

In order to fulfill the purpose of this research, quantitative style under the primary source of data through the use of self-administered questionnaire as a tool to ascertain the association between the promoting and challenging factors influencing adherence to ISO 45001 in Amazon's Company in the United State, after which the information gathered will be quantified in form of a number followed by the appropriate interpretation which allows for generalized conclusion on the subject matter tested in the study area.

These sources are the original documents or remain, standing as the first witness to a fact (Smith, 2010). A quantitative primary source will be used extensively in this study. The primary source used in this study was formulated questionnaire

➤ *Secondary Source*

The secondary source of data used in the process of this study is done through the use of online journals and articles pertaining to factors influencing adherence to ISO 45001 and occupational health and safety systems in general.

G. Data Collection Method

The researcher would obtain a research project attestation from his project supervisor for seeking permission and consent from the head of the selected section or department in Amazon's Company in the United State of America for the conduct of research making activity in the company and also have access to distribution of questionnaires to the selected audience. After this is done and approval is duly given to proceed with questionnaire administration, the questionnaire administering process will be done through proper maintenance of safety measures and protocols as stated by the World Health Organization based on the present pandemic disease "Covid-19". The researcher will be obliged to put on a safety face and nose mask thereby making sanitizer available for the interviewee for proper precaution to take effect. Hence, the researcher would distribute the questionnaires to the selected staff of Amazon's Company in the United State of America, while participants will be made voluntary. The researcher would ensure prompt completion and returns of all copies of the questionnaire. The completed copies of the questionnaires would be retrieved immediately from the respondents for data analysis.

H. Population and Sampling

The population of this study comprises all staff of Amazon's Company in the United State of America. While the sample will comprise 150 staff selected from the safety department of Amazon's Company in the United State of America. Thus, the selection of respondents will be purely based on conveniences as perceived by the respondents.

I. Ethics, Reliability and Validity

Based on the Ethics of this study, in order to attain successful outcome in this study and also avoid ethical issues from the targeted respondents sampled during the process of the study; the research will seek proper consent from the respondents will be done on their willingness to participate in the progress of the study, they will be assured of utmost confidentiality, the privacy of information given by them, as it will be treated as anonymous and will be used for research purpose only. Furthermore, appropriate references will be incorporated at the end of this study about the various authors cited in the body of this study.

The reliability of this study was obtained from the pilot testing done for reliability check on the consistency of the instrument developed for the study using the Cronbach alpha statistics for determining reliability coefficient. The statistics yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.787. However, based on the benchmark for acceptance of instrument reliability (1), this instrument was found to be reliable based on the benchmark, as it is standard enough to collect valid data from the respondents as regards factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 in Amazon's Company in the United State.

In order to ascertain the validity of this study instrument, the researcher's supervisor would review and validate the research instrument before its administration is done. This would be conducted in order to ensure the appropriateness of the instruments for the research purpose. All corrections would be duly effected to improve the quality of the questionnaire for the study. The validation would help in identifying items in the questionnaire that needed restating and eliminating those that are not important in the study.

J. Rationale

The choice of the above-chosen research methodologies is found to be worthy of this type of study. These research methodologies are capable of providing accurate information for the intended goal of the study, for it would give broader information on the internal and external factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 standard by the employee. The implication of this study would be an immense benefit to the committee in charge of occupational risk, for it would tender strategies for successful implementation of ISO 45001 in an

organization. It would also assist the producing companies like Amazon, SWOT, Target, Netflix, Apple, Google, etc in the adoption of task-specific standard operating procedures as a guideline for compliance to standards by employees and management. Furthermore, it will also be of benefit to the risk management trainer in that it would provide introductory information for standardized training of ISO 45001 in accordance to utilizing SWOT Analysis to determine the effect of internal and external factors on ISO 45001 effective implementation and would give details related to the exploration of the benefit of standard improvement in an organization.

Subsequently, as regards to chosen cross-sectional type as the time horizon to collect data for this study and the administration of questionnaire which coverage is between the period of 28 days, starting from 12th September to 10th October 2021 for appropriate analysis of the data collected. As well as the instrumentation part that deals with the use of a self-developed questionnaire which consists of 20 items with multiple choice and close-ended questionnaire will be designed to answer the research questions raised on the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon's Company in the United State of America, which tools are used as the instrument for data collection. Meanwhile, a non-probability convenience sampling technique will be utilized in this study. This procedure implies not giving the overall members of the population the opportunity to participate equally as being represented through selection in this research. Chosen respondents will rely upon the availability and willingness of the targeted sample to partake in this study. This is also a peculiar procedure to employ, as the respondents will come from different departments and the survey cannot include the entire population of every department in Amazon Company due to limited time. Respondents will be employees from different departments included under the compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon Company.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter deals with the analyses and results of the data collected for this study. The data were collected from 108 staff of Amazon's company in the United State of America. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, sample frequency, and percentage to describe the demographic data of the respondents and to answer research questions respectively.

A. Demographic characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Participants N=108

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	36.1
Female	60	55.6
Prefer Not To Say	9	8.3
Total	108	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-24	5	4.6
25-36	28	25.9
37-45	62	57.4
46-55	13	12.0
Race	Frequency	Percentage
Asian	38	35.2
Nigerian	28	25.9
Rest of Africa	38	35.2
Others	4	3.7
Major in the company	Frequency	Percentage
Engineering	28	25.9
Safety	47	43.5
Management	14	13.0
Health or hygiene	19	17.6
Total	108	100.0
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage

Bachelor's Degree	61	56.5
Master's Degree	47	43.5
Total	108	100.0

Table 2 shows the demographic information of the respondents on the basis of gender, age, race, major in the company, and Educational Qualification. Out of 108 (100%) Amazon staff that were sampled for this study, 60 (55.6%) were females and 39 (36.1%) were males. This indicates that the majority of the respondents were the female staff. Distribution of respondents by Age, 5(4.6%) falls within 18-24 age bracket, 28(25.9%) falls within 25-36 age bracket, meanwhile, 62(57.4%) of the respondents were between 37-45 age bracket, while the remaining 13(12.0%) were at their 46-55years age range. This implies that the majority of the staff working in Amazon were 37-45 years of age. . More so, according to the distribution of the respondents by Race, 38(35.2%) were Asian, 28(25.9%) were Nigerian, 38(35.2%) came together from rest of Africa, while the remaining 4(3.7%) of the respondents were other races like Middle Eastern and the rest. This indicated that the highest population of the staff working in Amazon in the United States of America were from Asia and the rest of Africa.

Furthermore, as shown in Table 2, distribution of respondents by their major in the company, 28(25.9%) majored in the Engineering department, 47(43.5%) majored in the Safety department, meanwhile, 14(13.0%) majored in Management, while the remaining 19(17.6%) of the respondents majored in Health and Hygiene department. This shows that the highest population of the staff working in Amazon in the United States of America sampled for this study majored in the Safety department. Also, the distribution of respondents by Educational Qualification, 61(56.5%) were Bachelor degree certificate holders, while the remaining 47(43.5%) have acquired their Master's Degree certificate. This implies that the majority of the staff working in Amazon Company in the United States of America have acquired their Bachelor's Degree certificate.

B. Answering of Research Objectives

The answers to the research Objectives were presented in simple frequency and percentage count with Mean and standard deviation tables.

- **General Research Objective:** To investigate the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management systems in Amazon company in the United States of America.

Table 2: The available Occupational Health and Safety Policy, any of these are regular terms that you are aware of its adoption effectiveness and implementation in a company.
Please select at least one

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
ISO 18001	30	27.8		
ISO 9001	11	10.2	2.44	0.498
ISO 14001	25	23.1		
ISO 45001	42	38.9		
Total	108	100.0	2.44	0.498

Table 2 presents the opinion of respondents on the available occupational health and safety policy in their company. However, the highest population 42(38.9%) of the respondents chose ISO45001 as the most identified policy to achieve full implementation in Amazon in the United States of America.

Table 3: For achievement of successful implantation of ISO 45001 for health and safety, which among these variables do you perceive to be a barrier, an issue or challenges

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Life cycle approach to OHS and system management	4	3.7		
Leadership mindset and corporate commitment	44	40.7	2.83	0.922
Regulatory framework and compliance	26	24.1		
Lack of awareness, Education and Training	34	31.5		
Total	108	100.0	2.83	0.922

Table revealed the variable perceived by the respondents to be a barrier, an issue, or challenge to a successful implementation of ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon company. Thus, the majority of the staff working in Amazon in the United States of America 44(40.7%) supported Leadership mindset and corporate commitment as the most perceived barrier to the successful implementation of ISO 45001.

Table 4: The implication of compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety would result to

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Positive reinforcement	4	3.7		
Use of propaganda like posters	11	10.2		
Proper selection of employers	24	22.2	3.46	0.825
Reduction is unsafe conditions	69	63.9		
Total	108	100.0		

As shown in Table 4, the opinion of respondents on the implication of ISO 45001, if it takes full implementation. However, the highest population of the staff working in Amazon in the United States of America chose reduction as an unsafe condition as an implication of ISO 45001 in the company.

Table 5: In order of compliance promotional preference, 1 being the most preferred, what factor appeals to you the most to promote adherence to ISO 45001 for health and safety in your company

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Ensure provision of written occupational health and safety policy in the company wards and sections	31	28.7		
Introduction of medical surveillance and orientation on the need for adherence done by guidance counsellors	25	23.1	2.46	1.172
Appointment of the health and safety committee	23	21.3		
provision of an opportunity for training on the OSH by the employer	29	26.9		
Total	108	100.0		

Table 5 presents the most appealing factors as perceived by the respondents to promote adherence to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon Company. Thus, the highest populations of the staff working in Amazon Company in the United States of America 31(28.7%) choose to ensure the provision of written occupational health and safety policy in the company world and sections.

The results presented in table 2, 3, 4 and 5 about the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system in Amazon Company in the United States of America was in line with the submission of Poon, et al.(2000) that the employee's compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system can be affected by some certain factors like the introduction of new production equipment or machines, market competition or demand pressure, swift change to new products, political instability caused by unexpected global disease outbreak and contextual restructure of the organization. Ultimately, employees' non-compliance to ISO 45001 could automatically expose them to high-risk operations and be liable to the continual occurrence of dangers that would emerge from the working environment, which gap should have been covered by due compliance to the management system policy.

Also, Silaparasetti, Rao & Khan (2017) similar studies on factors affecting the implementation of OHS management systems showed management commitment, staff participation, OHS training plus standard objectives were identified as instrumental to the implementation of OHS management systems. While, other similar results showed that management commitment linked with OHS policies, healthcare, communication, education, and training plays a vital part in sustaining a hazard-free workplace place in building construction projects.

- **Research Objective One:** To establish Challenges facing compliance to ISO 450001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States.

Tale 6: The motivational variables perceived as challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
the cost attached to the health and safety management system	52	48.1		
legal issues	14	13.0		
social responsibilities	19	17.6	2.12	1.228
Lack of health and safety management system	23	21.3		
Total	108	100.0		

Table 6 presents the opinion of respondents on preferred motivational variables perceived as challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon Company in the United States of America. However, the highest population of the staff working in Amazon companies in the United States of America represented by 52(48.1%) chose the cost attached to the health and safety Management system as the major challenges in the company as regards compliance to ISO 45001.

Table 7: The most preferred factor to be considered to identify the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State is

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Lack of interest in ISO 45001 policy	25	23.1		
sub-section management personal decision	28	25.9	2.56	1.130
lack of support from consulting firm	25	23.1		
ISO 45001 itself	30	27.8		
Total	108	100.0		

As shown in Table 7, the highest population of the respondents chose ISO 45001 itself to be the most preferred factor to be considered to identify the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon in the United States of America.

Table 8: If the cost of ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation and certification could be among the challenges facing it compliance, your most observed company cost rate is

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
don't want to disclose	9	8.3		
reasonable cost	5	4.6	3.19	0.870
cheaper	50	46.3		
Expensive	44	40.7		
Total	108	100.0	100.0	

In Table 8, the majority of the staff working in Amazon company supported cheaper as the most observed factor to be considered to identify the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon in the United States of America.

Table 9: If the external support from consulting firms could be among the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation, your most observed factor is

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Others	12	11.1		
Goals and plans	8	7.4		
Implementation management	32	29.6	4.04	1.824
Risk assessment	40	37.0		
Documentation	16	14.8		
Total	108	100.0		

Table 9 shows that risk assessment is the most observed factor to be considered if external support from consulting firms could be among the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation in the company, as this was chosen by 40(37.0%) being the highest population of the respondents.

Table 10: Noting that a fundamental principle is among the factors to guide policies to encourage compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, your most observed feature employ by your company is

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
medical examination of workers	14	13.0		
limited workloads	4	3.7		
guarding of machinery	12	11.1	3.92	1.388
general protection measures	25	23.1		
action monitoring and management	53	49.1		
Total	108	100.0		

In Table 10, insight is given on the respondent's opinion about the most preferred factor to guide policies to encourage compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. Thus, the highest population of the staff working in Amazon in the United States of America 53 represented by 49.1% chose action monitoring and management as the most observed feature employed by their company.

The above results presented in table 7,8,9,10 and 11 on factors challenging the compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in Amazon company in the United States of America contradict the findings of Kheni, Gibb, and Dainty (2010) that low literacy levels of workers, managers' ignorance of OHS responsibilities and ineffective OHS administration are basic factors hindering the capacity of construction SMEs to manage OHS effectively. Gaceri (2015) also examined the factors determining the implementation of OHS in Supermarkets. According to their search study, it was established that quality leadership style, employee training, and employee participation influenced the implementation of HS measures in supermarkets in Kenya. The participative approach on its own can bring in improvements on OHS as such managers are advised to share OHS information with employees in order to consolidate individualized relationships with them.

- **Research Objective Two:** To identify the factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

1. Table 11: Establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces is among the factors to guide policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

Options	Frequency	Percent
No Extent	11	10.2
Little Extent	10	
Small Extent	22	20.4
large extent	65	60.2
Total	108	100.0

Table 11 revealed that establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces is among the factors to guide policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, as it was rated by 81% (Small Extent 22(20.4%) and Large Extent 65 (60.2%) of the sampled workers to be among the identified factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

2. Table 12: Providing education and capacity-building opportunities for the employee and often providing advisory service are also key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of its adoption in your company is at

Options	Frequency	Percentage
No Extent	3	2.8
Little Extent	8	7.4
Small Extent	36	33.3
large extent	38	35.2
Very Large extent	23	21.3
Total	108	100.0

Table 12 revealed that establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces providing education and capacity building opportunities for the employee and often providing advisory service is also key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, as it was rated by 97% (Small Extent 36 (33.3%), Large Extent 38 (35.2%) and Very Large Extent 23 (21.3%)) of the sampled workers to be among the identified factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

3. Table 13: Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization is considered as another key step to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of its adoption in your company is at

Options	Frequency	Percent
Little Extent	8	7.4
Small Extent	44	40.7
large extent	52	48.1
Very Large extent	4	3.7
Total	108	100.0

It was indicated in Table 13 that introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization is considered as another key step to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, as it was rated by 82.6% (Small Extent 44 (40.7%), Large Extent 52 (48.1%) and Very Large Extent 4 (3.7%)) of the sampled workers to also be perceived as factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

4. Table 14: Creation of an enabling environment that allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems, and procedures, and the workforce in the organization is among the major ingredients required to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of its adoption in your company is at

Option	Frequency	Percent
No Extent	3	2.8
Little Extent	18	16.7
Small Extent	26	24.1
large extent	38	35.2
Very Large extent	23	21.3
Total	108	100.0

As shown in Table 14 the creation of enabling environment which allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization is among the major ingredient required to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, as it was identified by 80.6% (Small Extent 26 (24.1%), Large Extent 38 (35.2%) and Very Large Extent 23 (21.3%)) of the sampled workers as factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

5. Table 15: Optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to the safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment is also germane to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of its adoption in your company is at

Options	Frequency	Percent
Little Extent	11	10.2
Small Extent	36	33.3
large extent	38	35.2
Very Large extent	23	21.3
Total	108	100.0

Table 15 revealed that 89.8% (Small Extent 36 (33.3%), Large Extent 38 (35.2%) and Very Large Extent 23 (21.3%)) of the sampled workers identified optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to the safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment is also germane to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented to be among the factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

6. Table 16: Availability of provision for safety equipment or workable systems culture, in order to promote healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

Options	Frequency	Percent
Little Extent	24	22.2
Small Extent	23	21.3
large extent	38	35.2
Very Large extent	23	21.3
Total	108	100.0

According to data presented in the above Table 16, the availability of provision for safety equipment or workable systems culture, in order to promote a healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, as it was identified by 80.6% (Small Extent 23 (21.3%), Large Extent 38 (35.2%) and Very Large Extent 23 (21.3%)) of the sampled workers as one among the factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

However, the result presented in Tables 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 has shown that: i. establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces; ii. Providing education and capacity-building opportunities for the employee and often providing advisory service; iii. Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization; iv. creation of an enabling environment that allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization; v. optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to the safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment; and vi. The availability of provision for safety equipment or

workable systems culture, in order to promote a healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization, is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented were identified as the factors promoting compliance to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

This result gives credence to the findings of Geller (2005) that setting fundamental principles is among the factors to guide policies to encourage compliance of Occupational Health and Safety management system to be effectively implemented: action and management; general protection measures, for example, guarding of machinery, medical examination of young workers or limiting the weight of loads to be transported by a single worker; protection in specific branches of economic activity, such as mining, the building industry, commerce and dock work; protection of specific professions (for example, factory workers and seafarers) and categories of workers having particular occupational health needs (such as women or young workers); protection against specific risks (ionizing radiation, benzene, asbestos); prevention of occupational cancer; control of air pollution, noise, and vibration in the working environment; measures to ensure safety in the use of chemicals, including the prevention of major industrial accidents; organizational measures and procedures relating to labor inspection or compensation for occupational injuries and diseases.

This finding is also supported by the submission of Hughes and Ferrett (2011), that safety management is necessary at times to hold people accountable for doing the right things for injury prevention. However, management alone is not enough to achieve and sustain an injury-free workplace. Ontario Ministry of Labor (2013) submitted that ISO 45001 enables an organization to identify OH&S hazards, risks, and opportunities to proactively manage to support worker wellness/well-being. The ISO 45001 standard calls for the organization's management and leadership to integrate responsibility for health and safety issues as part of the organization's overall plan, demonstrate engagement with employees (and where they exist employees' representatives) to create an organizational culture that encourages the active participation of workers in the OH&S management system, as well as ensure the integration of OH&SMS into an organization's business process. Others are to understand and determine the scope and issues (positive and negative) that can affect how an organization manages the OH&S management system, determine risk and opportunities, develop or enhance OH&S policy and set objectives, and as well as gain a high-level understanding of needs and expectations of workers and other interested parties (and differences for managerial and non-managerial workers).

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the initial objectives and questions raised during the operations of this present study conducted on the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system of Amazon's Company in the United State of America.

After a conscientious detail elucidation has been conducted on the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system of Amazon's Company in the United State of America, the study conclusions are stated as follows:

A. Conclusions

Research Objective one (1) is to establish challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety standard in Amazon Company. The findings of the study therefore shows that the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety standard in Amazon Company are; i. the cost attached to health and safety management system under the motivational variables, ii. ISO 45001 itself, expensive cost of 45001 Health and Safety implementation as well as certification, iii. risk assessment from the external support of consulting firms. This implies that the problems confronting the compliance of employees to ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in United States was as a result of the cost required from staff to pay out of their salaries for the return of the services rendered to them by the Health and Safety management. The expensive nature of the cost attached to adoption of ISO 45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in United States would either way cause disloyalty from the path of the workers and denial to accept the policy stipulated under ISO 45001 itself.

The research objective two (2) was to identify the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America. The study conclusions on objective two (2) suggested that; i. the establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces; ii. Educational provision and capacity building opportunity for the employee and often provide advisory service; iii. Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization; iv. creation of enabling environment which allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization; optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment; and v. the availability of provision for safe equipments or workable systems culture for the promotion of healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization as the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America.

B. Recommendations

The study recommendations drawn from the above conclusions are as follows:

- Research Objective one (1) is to establish challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety standard in Amazon Company. The study therefore recommended that the company head should be ready for sensitizing their employees on the importance of their adherence to principles and policies if ISO45001 for Occupational Health and Safety system, thereby stating all requirements and likely implications attracted by their failure to comply accordingly. Also, the company should take appropriate steps to fine tune the challenges encountered for the achievement of employees adherence to the policy of ISO45001. The employer should ensure adequate establishment of advisory service on a regular basis, the will be of great assistance, as the process will be use to persuade and encourage the employees to show positive attitude to the company's stated policies as regards to their compliance rules and regulations of Iso45001 for Occupational Health and safety system to take its full implementation in the company.

- The research objective two (2) was to identify the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America. The study recommended that Amazon's company should be ready to adopt an ideal control measure in their company, most especially in the production department. Implementation of such baseline will go a long way to forestall appropriate direction and will make it easy to coordinate the overall affairs of the workers in term of cooperativeness to authority and command.

The company department leaders should also ensure to build cordial relationship with the inferior employee, this will enable free flow of information and interactions about all that is beneficial can be easily included among the matter arising or discussion point such like having a sensitization talk for few minutes to buy their interest to render appropriate support for the adherence to ISO45001 for Occupational Health and Safety.

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APPENDIX I

Factors Influencing Compliance to ISO 45001 for Health and Safety in Amazon company of United State

Questionnaire Draft

My name is Olumide Adeniyi, currently conducting a research for my postgraduate (MBA program) in Health and safety Leadership at the Catholic University of Murcia, Spain. I will be happy to have you spare some minutes to respond to the survey as it will enable me complete my dissertation. Please be assured that all responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality and only used for the purpose of the study. Below are some statements, kindly tick (✓) the option in front of each item that is most applicable to you. Thanking you for your anticipated co-corporation.

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Q1. Gender

- Male
- Female

Q2. Age range

- 18 – 24yrs
- 25 – 36yrs
- 37 – 45yrs
- 46 – 55yrs
- Above 55yrs

Q3. Race:

- Asian
- American
- European
- Nigerian
- Rest of Africa
- Others, please specify _____

Q4. What is your major in the company

- a. Health or hygiene
- b. Environment
- c. Management
- d. Safety
- e. Engineering
- f. Other [Please specify _____]

Q5. Educational Qualification

- a. Diploma
- b. Bachelor's degree
- c. Master's Degree
- d. Ph.D/ DBA
- e. Other [Please specify _____]

General Research Objective on the factors influencing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety management system in Amazon Company in the United States of America

Q6. Within the available Occupational Health and Safety Policy, any of these are regular terms that you are aware of its adoption effectiveness and implementation in a company. Please select at least one

- a. ISO 18001
- b. ISO 9001
- c. ISO 14001
- d. ISO 45001

Q7. For achievement of successful implantation of ISO 45001 for health and safety, which among these variables do you perceive to be a barrier, an issue or challenges

- a. Lack of awareness, Education and Training
- b. Regulatory framework and compliance
- c. Leadership mindset and corporate commitment
- d. Life cycle approach to OHS and system management

Q8. The implication of compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety would result to

- a. Reduction is unsafe conditions
- b. Proper selection of employers
- c. Use of propaganda like posters
- d. Positive re-enforcement

Q9. In order of compliance promotional preference, 1 being the most preferred, what factor appeal to you the most to promote adherence to ISO 45001 for health and safety in your company

- a. provision of an opportunity for training on the OSH by the employer
- b. Appointment of the health and safety committee
- c. Introduction of medical surveillance and orientation on the need for adherence done by guidance counselors
- d. Ensure provision of written occupational health and safety policy in the company wards and sections

Q10. Which among these motivational variables do you perceive as challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State

- a. Lack of health and safety management system
- b. social responsibilities
- c. legal issues
- d. cost attached to health and safety management system

Specific Research Objective One (1) on Challenges facing compliance to ISO 450001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in United States

Q11. The most preferred factor to be considered to identify the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State is

- a. ISO 45001 itself
- b. lack of support from consulting firm
- c. sub-section management personal decision
- d. Lack of interest in ISO 45001 policy

Q12. If the cost of ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation and certification could be among the challenges facing it compliance, your most observed company cost rate is

- a. Expensive
- b. cheaper
- c. reasonable cost
- d. don't want to disclose

Q13. If the external support from consulting firms could be among the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation, your most observed factor is

- a. Policy
- b. Documentation
- c. Organization and responsibility
- d. Risk assessment
- e. Training and communication
- f. Implementation management
- g. Goals and plans
- h. Others [please specify _____]

Q14. Noting that a fundamental principles is among the factors to guide policies to encourage compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, your most observed feature employ by your company is

- a. action monitoring and management
- b. general protection measures
- c. guarding of machinery
- d. limited workloads
- e. medical examination of workers

Q15. Establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces is among the factors to guide policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

Specific Research Objective Two (2) on the factors promoting compliance to ISO45001 Health and Safety standards in the Amazon Company in the United States of America

Q16. Providing education and capacity building opportunity for the employee and often provide advisory services is also key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

Q17. Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization is consider as another key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

Q18. Creation of enabling environment which allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization is among the major ingredient required to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

Q19. Optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment is also germane to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

Q20. Availability of provision for safe equipments or workable systems culture, in order to promote healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

- a. No extent
- b. Little extent
- c. Small extent
- d. Large extent
- e. Very large extent

APPENDIX II

SPSS RAW DATA ANALYSIS OUTPUT RESULT

what is your gender?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Prefer Not to say	9	8.3	8.3	8.3
	Female	60	55.6	55.6	63.9
	Male	39	36.1	36.1	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

what is your Age?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-24	5	4.6	4.6	4.6
	25-36	28	25.9	25.9	30.6
	37-45	62	57.4	57.4	88.0
	46-55	13	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

what s your race?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Others	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	Rest of africa	38	35.2	35.2	38.9
	Nigeran	28	25.9	25.9	64.8
	Asian	38	35.2	35.2	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

What is your major in the company

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Engineering	28	25.9	25.9	25.9
	Safety	47	43.5	43.5	69.4
	Management	14	13.0	13.0	82.4
	Health or hygiene	19	17.6	17.6	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

what is your educational qualificaton?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor's Degree	61	56.5	56.5	56.5
	Master's Degree	47	43.5	43.5	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

the available Occupational Health and Safety Policy, any of these are regular terms that you are aware of its adoption effectiveness and implementation in a company. Please select at least one

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	ISO 18001	30	27.8	27.8	27.8
	ISO 9001	11	10.2	10.2	38.0
	ISO 14001	25	23.1	23.1	61.1
	ISO 45001	42	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

For achievement of successful implantation of ISO 45001 for health and safety, which among these variables do you perceive to be a barrier, an issue or challenges

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Life cycle approach to OHS and system management	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	Leadership mindset and corporate commitment	44	40.7	40.7	44.4
	Regulatory framework and compliance	26	24.1	24.1	68.5
	Lack of awareness, Education and Training	34	31.5	31.5	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

The implication of compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety would result to

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Positive re-enforcement	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	Use of propaganda like posters	11	10.2	10.2	13.9
	Proper selection of employers	24	22.2	22.2	36.1
	Reduction is unsafe conditions	69	63.9	63.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

In order of compliance promotional preference, 1 being the most preferred, what factor appeal to you the most to promote adherence to ISO 45001 for health and safety in your company

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Ensure provision of written occupational health and safety policy in the company wards and sections	31	28.7	28.7	28.7
	Introduction of medical surveillance and orientation on the need for adherence done by guidance counselors	25	23.1	23.1	51.9
	Appointment of the health and safety committee	23	21.3	21.3	73.1
	provision of an opportunity for training on the OSH by the employer	29	26.9	26.9	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Which among these motivational variables do you perceive as challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	cost attached to health and safety management system	52	48.1	48.1	48.1
	legal issues	14	13.0	13.0	61.1
	social responsibilities	19	17.6	17.6	78.7
	Lack of health and safety management system	23	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

The most preferred factor to be considered to identify the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety in the Amazon Company in United State is

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Lack of interest in ISO 45001 policy	25	23.1	23.1	23.1
	sub-section management personal decision	28	25.9	25.9	49.1
	lack of support from consulting firm	25	23.1	23.1	72.2
	ISO 45001 itself	30	27.8	27.8	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

If the cost of ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation and certification could be among the challenges facing it compliance, your most observed company cost rate is

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	don't want to disclose	9	8.3	8.3	8.3
	reasonable cost	5	4.6	4.6	13.0
	cheaper	50	46.3	46.3	59.3
	Expensive	44	40.7	40.7	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

. If the external support from consulting firms could be among the challenges facing compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation, your most observed factor is

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Others	12	11.1	11.1	11.1
	Goals and plans	8	7.4	7.4	18.5
	Implementation management	32	29.6	29.6	48.1
	Risk assessment	40	37.0	37.0	85.2
	Documentation	16	14.8	14.8	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Noting that a fundamental principles is among the factors to guide policies to encourage compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented, your most observed feature employ by your company is

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	medical examination of workers	14	13.0	13.0	13.0
	limited workloads	4	3.7	3.7	16.7
	guarding of machinery	12	11.1	11.1	27.8
	general protection measures	25	23.1	23.1	50.9
	action monitoring and management	53	49.1	49.1	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Establishing legislation and regulations for OHS in workplaces is among the factors to guide policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No Extent	11	10.2	10.2	10.2
	Little Extent	10	9.3	9.3	19.4
	Small Extent	22	20.4	20.4	39.8
	large extent	65	60.2	60.2	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Providing education and capacity building opportunity for the employee and often provide advisory services is also key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in yo

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No Extent	3	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Little Extent	8	7.4	7.4	10.2
	Small Extent	36	33.3	33.3	43.5
	large extent	38	35.2	35.2	78.7
	Very Large extent	23	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Introducing motivational programs and heightening sensitization is consider as another key steps to policies to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The level of it adoption in your company is at

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Little Extent	8	7.4	7.4	7.4
	Small Extent	44	40.7	40.7	48.1
	large extent	52	48.1	48.1	96.3
	Very Large extent	4	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Creation of enabling environment which allows easy interactions between the working equipment, systems and procedures, and the workforce in the organization is among the major ingredient required to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No Extent	3	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Little Extent	18	16.7	16.7	19.4
	Small Extent	26	24.1	24.1	43.5
	large extent	38	35.2	35.2	78.7
	Very Large extent	23	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Optimal concentration on the attitudes and values attached to safety of workers and other crucial influential factors for health and safety enactment is also germane to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. T

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Little Extent	11	10.2	10.2	10.2
	Small Extent	36	33.3	33.3	43.5
	large extent	38	35.2	35.2	78.7
	Very Large extent	23	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Availability of provision for safe equipments or workable systems culture, in order to promote healthy and safe working lifestyle in the organization is essential to promote compliance of ISO 45001 for health and safety to be effectively implemented. The

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percer	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Little Extent	24	22.2	22.2	22.2
	Small Extent	23	21.3	21.3	43.5
	large extent	38	35.2	35.2	78.7
	Very Large extent	23	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

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the available Occupational Health and Safety Policy, any of these are regular terms that you are aware of its adoption effectiveness and implementation in a company. Please select at least one

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The implication of compliance to ISO 45001 for health and safety would result to

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If the cost of ISO 45001 for health and safety implementation and certification could be among the challenges facing it compliance, your most observed company cost rate is

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